

Examining Efl Students' Views Of Intercultural Communication During The COVID-19 Pandemic

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Abstract

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, there have been increased news reports pertaining to racism, discrimination, and intercultural relation issues. The aim of this case study was to explore South Korean EFL students' views of the importance of intercultural communication and how they perceive intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic. It also sought to obtain participant recommendations on how to improve awareness of intercultural communication. This study was conducted during the spring semester of 2020 at a university in central South Korea. Participants included 14 South Korean university students who were enrolled in an intercultural communication class that was conducted online. Data included individual interviews, a focus group, and essays. Data analysis centered on examining commonalities and key statements made by participants. In terms of why it is important to study intercultural communication, results highlighted the need for people to be understanding and knowledgeable about diverse cultures, having respect for other people and cultures, and ensuring that past intercultural conflict does not happen in the future. Students shared their opinions on several intercultural issues in the news germane to the COVID-19 pandemic, including discrimination toward Asians as well as other topics including the Black Lives Matter movement, and issues affecting Korea. Students provided a wide range of recommendations for improving their awareness of intercultural communication including reading about other cultures, interacting with diverse people on social media, watching cultural videos, being more accepting and open minded, and studying historical events related to intercultural communication.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in myriad challenges and unprecedented changes, which have impacted various facets of everyday life. Many social ills plaguing society including discrimination and racism have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. It has been connected to certain locations and ethnicities, which has resulted in discriminatory actions against specific groups of people (Li et al., 2020). Inaccurate or fake news has also been reported on social media, which has been detrimental for specific populations during the COVID-19 crisis (Shimizu, 2020), and some media outlets have stressed that the pandemic originated in China (Zheng, Goh, & Wen, 2020). People of Asian descent have experienced increased rates of discrimination due to the pandemic (King, Leow, Cabarkapa, & Ng, 2020). Stigmas have also arisen because of prejudicial views and discriminatory actions that have targeted specific groups (Li et al., 2020). It is critical for society to be educated on the disease and to not target or label specific groups or individuals.

Myriad reports have shown the injurious impact of prejudicial views and discriminatory actions that have been directed at specific groups. There has also been an uptick in global discrimination of people from China and other Asian backgrounds (King, Leow, Cabarkapa, & Ng, 2020). Research from the Understanding America Study indicated that Asian Americans were 4.1 times more likely to face coronavirus-based discrimination in comparison to non-Hispanic whites (Liu & Finch, 2020). Specific groups in other countries have also become victims of discrimination and hate crimes. For example, Muslims in India and Roma communities in northern Spain have been targets of COVID-19 related discrimination (UNESCO, 2020a). Furthermore, there have been increased reports of discrimination toward healthcare workers, supermarket employees, and the homeless (UNESCO, 2020a). According to UNESCO (2020a), "in times of crisis and great uncertainty, especially of such magnitude as the one we are currently experiencing, people tend to look for scapegoats in order to vent their frustrations, worries and fears" (para. 10). Specific groups have been victimized and targeted throughout the pandemic and have even been blamed for the virus.

In South Korea, a COVID-19 outbreak occurred in Itaewon, which is a district frequented by foreigners (Ock, 2020). After this outbreak, there were reports of foreigners who felt that they had been discriminated

against and were asked to be tested even if they had not been to Itaewon. In November 2020, the National Human Rights Commission of Korea published a report on foreign resident's human rights during the COVID-19 pandemic (as cited in Lee, 2020). The data had been collected from 307 foreigners living in Korea. One in three stated that they had experienced discrimination that had been attributed to the COVID-19 pandemic. These forms of discrimination include hostile comments online and in daily life and facing issues on public transportation and in restaurants and cafes. Aside from general challenges in society that impacted healthcare, business, education, and various other sectors, troubling news reports of racism, discrimination, and other issues pertaining to intercultural relations surfaced during the pandemic. These issues are connected to intercultural communication, and were thus addressed in the course to further examine problems impacting society and the world as whole during the pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic dominated the news in 2020; however, there have been numerous other events both domestically in South Korea and internationally that are significantly related to intercultural issues including but not limited to the Black Lives Matters movement, major political elections, relations between North and South Korea, cancelling of the summer 2020 Olympics, issues of white supremacy and racism, and the UK formally withdrawing from the European Union. Some of these issues have many direct and indirect connections to the COVID-19 pandemic. The purpose of this study was to gain insight into South Korean EFL students' views of the importance of intercultural communication and how they perceive intercultural communication issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, it sought to obtain recommendations from South Korean EFL students to improve intercultural communication. At the time of this writing, there was a paucity of research on intercultural communication that directly relates to the COVID-19 pandemic. Learning more about students' perceptions of intercultural communication and news issues during this critical period can aid in developing and enhancing future intercultural communication courses and other classes that incorporate intercultural communication themes into the curriculum. The following research questions were used to guide the study:

- 1) How do South Korean EFL students describe the importance of intercultural communication?
- 2) How do South Korean EFL students perceive intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic?
- 3) What recommendations do South Korean EFL students have to improve awareness of intercultural communication?

Literature Review

Intercultural Communication

Intercultural communication is "an on-going critically reflexive process involving the development of skills, attitudes and knowledge, necessary for interacting with people from diverse cultural backgrounds" (Walton, Priest, & Paradies, 2013, p. 181). The era of globalization has led to a highly interconnected world thus necessitating awareness of intercultural communication. This can be achieved through knowledge of diverse cultures, making comparisons between an individual's culture and other cultures, and reflecting on what is learned about cultural differences (Kramsch, 1998). In the English language learning context, learning about intercultural communication is also vital since English is the international language of communication and serves as the lingua franca in many settings. English language classrooms play a critical role in preparing students to communicate in international settings, and thus learning about other cultures and how to interact with people from diverse backgrounds is essential (Crozet & Liddicoat, 1999). Byram, Gribkova, and Starkey (2002) discussed the role of intercultural communication in the classroom for helping students to learn to respect other cultures and appreciate differences between cultures. English language learners should be cognizant of cultural diversity. English is a global language, and students are expected to communicate with people from various cultures and backgrounds.

2020 has been a pivotal year in modern history with many formidable challenges. However, crises can also provide opportunities for introspection and development. Intercultural communication has been significantly impacted as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. Schwartz (2020) recommends that intercultural researchers seek ways to use coronavirus related topics in their studies. According to Schwartz (2020), "This pandemic is a historical moment that will have a lasting effect on the ways in which people, communities, and nations relate to one another" (p. 2). During the COVID-19 pandemic, there were increased reports of social stigmas, prejudice, and discriminatory actions based on ethnicity and places of origin (Li et al., 2020). According to UNESCO (2020b), "The need for dialogue during COVID-19 not only exposed vulnerabilities and inequalities but also caused new forms of discrimination that require urgent action by governments, civil society activists, and health practitioners" (p. 4). Although the COVID-19 pandemic dominated the news in 2020, there were a wide range of other reports related to intercultural issues. Educators also must play a role in teaching students about issues pertaining to intercultural communication and strive to create a classroom that promotes active engagement in local communities, society, and the world.

Global Citizenship Education

In the classroom, it is critical to create a climate which centers on better understanding of diversity. According to UNESCO (2014), global citizenship education “aims to empower learners to engage and assume active roles, both locally and globally, to face and resolve global challenges and ultimately to become proactive contributors to a more just, peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, secure and sustainable world” (p. 15). Global citizenship education has been applied to a wide range of educational settings and has also been adopted in Korean educational contexts (e.g. Cho, 2017; Cho & Mosselson, 2018). Global citizenship education is centered on valuing human rights and cultural differences, while supporting peaceful methods for dealing with conflicts across cultures (Hyo, 2017). It also aims to foster active engagement in society (O’Dowd, 2019) and encourage students to become “current and future contributors to global society” (Leask, 2015, p. 17). Students can take on an active role in being agents for transformative change. Moreover, it should equip students with the resources and knowledge needed to improve intercultural communication and other issues impacting society.

The theory of global citizenship education has been applied to English language learning settings. Porto and Byram (2015) highlight that foreign language classes should also prepare students for “intercultural citizenship” (p. 10). Hyo (2017) reported that students had favorable views of participating in English language learning courses, which stress global citizenship education and intercultural communication. In Hyo’s (2017) study, students participated in lectures on culture and global citizenship, took part in a global citizen day with guest speakers, completed group activities, corresponded with pen pals through email and video chat, and completed a cultural compare and contrast assignment. By incorporating key elements of global citizenship education into intercultural communication classes for English language learners, students may increase their awareness and appreciation of cultural diversity. Moreover, global citizenship education aims to encourage active participation in society. By focusing on elements of global citizenship education, students may be more inclined to apply what they have learned in intercultural communication courses to the real world and consider how their thoughts and actions impact other people.

Methodology

This descriptive case study was conducted during the last month of the spring semester of 2020 at a university in central South Korea. Participants included 14 South Korean university students who were enrolled in an intercultural communication class that was conducted online. Participants were obtained through purposive and convenience sampling (Creswell, 2007). The course highlighted principles of intercultural competency and global citizenship education. These principles include:

respecting the values of people from different cultures, being open minded towards them, getting as much information as possible about other cultures, accepting the ideas of people from different cultures, getting rid of prejudice, approaching positively towards fellows with different cultures, being friendly, self-confident, and conducting them with propriety while communicating, and so on (Tuncel&Paker, 2018, p. 200).

Furthermore, the instructor emphasized the need to be an agent for change in society, which is a central tenet of global citizenship education. The course was intended to be an on-campus class, but due to the urgent need for social distancing, courses were taught online. Students were required to participate in two live, 90-minute classes each week over the course of a 16-week semester. Primary topics discussed in class include defining culture, cultural analysis, cultural norms, cultural identity, culture shock, stereotypes, racism, prejudice, discrimination, verbal and nonverbal communication, diversity issues, ethnocentrism, intercultural issues in the news, collectivism and individualism, high and low context cultures, belief systems, migration, and intercultural film analysis. Most classes consisted of a short lecture, small group and partner activities, video clips, discussions, and individual reflection activities. Students also completed several homework assignments, a midterm and final exam, and presented on intercultural communication topics.

Data included individual interviews, a focus group, and essays. Data were collected through telephone, Zoom, and MS Word submissions that were uploaded to the university learning management system. Individual telephone interviews were conducted with all students to learn more about their perceptions of intercultural communication topics. The average telephone interview was 10 to 15 minutes. Questions asked include:

- 1) Why is intercultural communication important?
- 2) Can you think of some examples in which intercultural communication is important?
- 3) Have you ever experienced intercultural communication?
- 4) If so, can you explain your experience/experiences?
- 5) Can you think of an example/examples of intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic?
- 6) How do you feel about this issue/s?
- 7) What recommendations do you have to improve awareness of intercultural communication in your personal life?

- 8) What recommendations do you have to improve awareness of intercultural communication on campus?
- 9) What recommendations do you have to improve awareness of intercultural communication in society?
- 10) Do you have any other thoughts related to these topics that you would like to share?

A semi-structured focus group was conducted with course participants through Zoom. The instructor sought to gain more clarity about the participants' interview responses. The interview questions were asked again, but the instructor sought to gain more details and clarification by asking follow-up questions. The focus group lasted 20 minutes. Finally, students completed essays at the end of the semester to reflect on course topics. Each response was required to be at least a paragraph. Since writing takes considerably longer than speaking, students were only required to write three short essays. The questions included: 1. Why is intercultural communication important? Provide some examples. 2. Can you think of an example of an intercultural communication issue in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic? How do you feel about this issue? 3. What recommendations do you have to improve awareness of intercultural communication? Data analysis focused on examining commonalities and key statements made by participants (Creswell, 2007). Coding was used to identify similar themes that emerged. Participants were assigned a pseudonym to protect their identities.

Results

Research question one sought to gain insight into how South Korean EFL students describe the importance of intercultural communication. There were several primary results extrapolated from the data, which include having awareness of diverse cultures, being respectful of other people and cultures, and ensuring that past intercultural conflict does not happen in the future. Selected excerpts of students' responses are included to gain a more holistic understanding of their views.

Describing the Importance of Intercultural Communication

Awareness of Diverse Cultures

A dominant theme discussed by participants was the need to be aware of diverse cultures. This topic was discussed by 10 of the participants. Jeongsu (male) provided a detailed perspective on the importance of learning about different cultures. He stated:

Globalization has continued all over the world. Now you can work or communicate with people of different cultures. However, if you don't know about cultural differences, you might be rude while communicating with people of different cultures. Wherever we go, there are different rules of culture. Sometimes we might judge their cultural rules in shock and think they are weird. However, if we judge cultural values solely from our own standards, there is no more communication. To avoid making this mistake, we have to study intercultural communication. By studying, I have a more open mind. The world is no longer isolated, and mutual respect is essential.

He emphasized the importance of globalization, which has led to vast changes in how communication takes place and how people need to learn about other cultures, and not just famous countries. He also discussed how a lack of awareness of intercultural communication can lead to miscommunication and other barriers. This was reiterated by Jina (female) who said, "Intercultural communication is a form of global communication. We need to understand each other even if we grew up in different environments. If we don't, this can lead to miscommunication and problems." Hyeok Gi (male) discussed the importance of reducing communication problems. He said, "There are many reasons why we need to study intercultural communication, but the most important is to reduce misunderstanding. We have to be more accepting to reduce problems and barriers."

Participants also mentioned that intercultural communication is more than simply talking to people from different cultures. Cheolsu (male) stated that it is important to recognize the differences between cultures and understand these differences more. He said, "It is important to learn the language, but being aware of nonverbal expressions is also critical. After all, the overall understanding of other cultures helps avoid conflict and improve communication." Jihoon (male) provided some examples of cultural misunderstanding that result from a lack of education about cultural diversity.

Culture is a strong part of people's lives. It is related to their values, humor, hopes, and business. There are many events that have occurred because of not understanding other cultures. My second major is business, and there are many examples of business failing because of a lack of cultural awareness.

Students provided a wide array of examples germane to the importance of learning about diverse cultures. The world is largely interconnected and learning about diverse people is critical. Even if students do not travel or encounter foreigners in their own countries, they are likely to be exposed to foreigners and other cultures through online exchanges.

Being Respectful of Other People and Cultures

Five students discussed the importance of being respectful of other people and cultures. By showing respect for other people and cultures, greater understanding and mutual appreciation can occur. Jeongbin (female) provided an in-depth discussion of the importance of respect.

In society, people live by communicating with many people. In particular, people with diverse cultures interact with each other more. However, if the culture is different, the way of thinking is likely to be different. If the thinking system is different, there is a high possibility of communication problems. Behavior with good intentions in one's own culture can be one with bad intentions in another. This can cause problems in human relationships. If we learn the differences between different cultures and our own, we can reduce the above mistakes. In other words, we can learn the communication style of respect and consideration. We can eliminate prejudices and stereotypes. By abandoning the stereotypes that were inherent and communicating with people from different cultures, we can have a broad view.

Sumi (female) expanded on the importance of respect and stated,

We are living in a globalized world. We have to constantly interact with people from different cultural backgrounds, not only physically but virtually on the Internet. Especially nowadays, being politically correct is highly debated among people, hence the importance of knowing other cultures became a must rather than a choice. People have different customs and values depending on where they are from. Having cultural awareness and knowing how to treat others is the fundamental way to be respectful. On the other hand, ignorance can cause a lot of issues such as ethnocentrism and hatred.

Other examples centered on the importance of respect for showing appreciation of other cultures. Even though mistakes may be made because of language or cultural barriers, showing respect can go a long way. Two students also mentioned the dangers of ethnocentrism and xenophobia and emphasized the need to be respectful and appreciative of cultural diversity.

Past Intercultural Conflict

Five students discussed the importance of ensuring that past intercultural conflict does not continue, especially by studying historical intercultural conflict. For example, Minho (male) elaborated on the historical tensions between Japan and Korea and discussed the need to be knowledgeable about history, which influences modern intercultural communication and relations between countries and people. He stated,

Firstly, intercultural communication is a way to learn about other unfamiliar cultures. For example, I talked about the Rising Sun flag in my first discussion. It is a symbol of a painful history that occurred during the Japanese colonial era. However, some cultures are not familiar with this history. To prevent problems, it is important to learn about history and culture.

Two other students also discussed Japanese and Korean relations. Taeho (male) mentioned the importance of remembering history to prevent past mistakes from happening again.

In order for discrimination to decrease, understanding of other cultures is essential. We need to understand and respect each other's culture now. We should not repeat history. Still in the world, discrimination and conflict between different cultures, continues to rise. We must move on to a better future for our descendants.

Students mentioned that society has an obligation to learn history so that mistakes of the past do not continue. Other historical examples mentioned by students that had previously been discussed in class include the Holocaust, the genocide in Rwanda and the Balkans, the Civil Rights Movement, apartheid, and the Killing Fields in Cambodia.

Perceptions of Intercultural Issues in the News During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The second research question aimed to learn about how South Korean EFL students perceive intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students discussed their thoughts on several intercultural issues in the news that are pertinent to the COVID-19 pandemic, including discrimination toward Asians as well as other topics including the Black Lives Matter movement, and issues affecting Korea. Specific examples and excerpts are provided.

COVID-19: Discrimination

Intercultural communication issues pertaining to the COVID-19 pandemic tended to dominate discussions and class activities throughout the semester. Unsurprisingly, 11 students discussed issues directly related to COVID-19 and discrimination. For example, Jeongsu (male) stated:

Intercultural communication starts with mutual respect and understanding others. However, many people lack mutual respect. Especially racism, which is the biggest problem added to a lack of intercultural communication. Recently, racism is increasing all over the world. Racist YouTube videos related to the virus have drawn attention. Some western people are racist to Asian people with the virus. Many people are suffering. They have lost their jobs, and we live a different life because of the virus. I am not the only one who is having a hard time. In times like this, we should respect and understand each other more.

Seri (female) shared similar thoughts and said, "From the beginning of this year, people all around the world were harassed because of the coronavirus. I heard stories about Koreans in other countries experiencing problems and foreigners living in Korea. There were many issues related to discrimination." Stories of discrimination in Korea were also shared. Jina (female) stated, "We see stories of people blaming foreigners for coronavirus spread. Here in Korea, there was an outbreak in the foreigner district, Itaewon. Koreans overseas

are facing discrimination too.” Students provided various examples of discrimination pertaining to COVID-19, both domestically and internationally, but most examined international issues.

Black Lives Matter Movement: Racism, Prejudice, and Discrimination

Issues pertaining to racism, prejudice, and discrimination, were also commonly discussed, especially in relation to the Black Lives Matter movement. Eight students provided examples related to these topics, some of which were discussed during class lectures. One student had previously done a class presentation on the Black Lives Matter movement, so the class had some background information on the topic and were aware of stories in the news pertaining to the movement. Students provided several examples of the Black Lives Matter movement and how it has impacted the United States and the world. For example, Seongjin (male) stated, “The Black Lives Matter movement has changed the world. It is important for people to know about the struggles of black people and to make changes in society through action.” Three students discussed the case of George Floyd and connections to the Black Lives Matter movement. Students provided specific examples of stories related to racism, prejudice, and discrimination and focused more directly on how the Black Lives Matter movement has brought racial issues to the forefront.

Korean Issues

Four students discussed issues that were relevant to the Korean peninsula, especially relations between North and South Korea. Students mentioned how progress with North Korea had been made in recent years; however, some challenges recently arose between the two countries making communication more difficult. According to Garam (female),

I recently read an article about President Moon Jae In’s speech regarding the Korean War. He said, ‘We pursue peace and intend to live well together. We will continuously search for routes that are mutually beneficial for both Koreas through peace. Before speaking, I hope that we can become friendly neighbors first.’ I agree with this speech. It is necessary to know about North Korea’s culture first before talking about unification. The Korean War ceasefire took place in 1953. The war was a tragic event in Korean history. This resulted from ideological differences. I hope this kind of conflict is never repeated. I hope the two Koreas give each other reconciliation rather than weapons.

Two students discussed issues pertaining to multicultural families and the hardships that their children face in the South Korean education system. Issues impacting North and South Korean relations as well as the challenges of a multicultural society in South Korea were discussed.

Recommendations for Improving Awareness of Intercultural Communication

The third research question sought to get recommendations on how to improve awareness of intercultural communication. Students provided a wide range of recommendations for improving awareness of intercultural communication including reading about other cultures, interacting with diverse people on social media, watching cultural videos, being more accepting and open minded, and studying historical events related to intercultural communication. Some specific examples of student recommendations are provided.

Personal and Societal Learning

Students discussed several ideas for improving personal and societal awareness of intercultural communication. Sumi (female) stated that people should continue to study other cultures, be open minded without prejudice, and when learning something new, try to have a neutral stance. “Learn about origins of cultures, historical context of cultural customs, learn more about history, and don’t stay silent when you hear culturally offensive jokes.” Jihoon (male) stated,

The most important thing is to have mutual respect and be open minded. If you think your culture is the best and look down on other cultures, you cannot communicate across cultures. You also should learn other languages. Communicate through language and enter their culture directly and learn more deeply.

Some students provided more practical examples that can be more easily achieved in the social distancing period. For example, Sanghyeok (male) recommended YouTube cultural videos and interacting with foreigners through Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Suhee (female) recommended watching Korean TV shows that center on intercultural communication themes including “Where is my Friend’s House,” “Grandfather’s over Flowers,” and “Non-Summit Meeting.” She also mentioned the importance of learning about different education systems to examine how studying and learning varies across the world.

On Campus

Additional recommendations focused on programs and activities that could be implemented on campus. Students provided several recommendations, which include increasing classes and programs related to intercultural communication, promoting mentoring programs, and providing more opportunities for intercultural exchange. For example, Hyerin (female) mentioned increasing the number of classes and programs on intercultural communication and to promote friendship and mentoring programs for students from other cultures. She stated that she will focus more on her prejudices and understanding of other cultures. She also has been fearful to approach foreign students at the university. “There are foreign students at my university, but I’ve been afraid to approach them. We have to reach out and get to know diverse people though.” She also stated that it is important to have more time to communicate together. This was also reiterated by Jihoon (male) who has a

strong interest in meeting foreign friends. He stated, “We need more projects and programs to interact with foreign students on campus.” Students vocalized the importance of interacting more with foreign students and engaging in cross cultural communication activities. Students considered various ways that they could improve their awareness of intercultural communication in different settings and promote change in their personal lives, on campus, and in society.

Discussion

Research question one aimed to learn more about South Korean EFL students’ views of the importance of intercultural communication. Three primary results emerged included having awareness of diverse cultures, being respectful of other people and cultures, and ensuring that past intercultural conflict does not happen in the future. The course focused on the importance of reflection and deeper understanding of diverse cultures. Kramsch (1998) emphasizes that intercultural communication can be improved through awareness of other cultures, comparing one’s own culture to other cultures, and reflecting on what is learned in regard to cultural differences. This course aimed to achieve these objectives, and students considered methods for improving their understanding of intercultural communication. Byran, Gribkova, and Starkey (2002) state that it is critical for students to respect other cultures and value the differences between cultures. Students provided several concrete examples that focus on the importance of intercultural communication and how further development and reflection is needed to improve understanding and interaction in cross cultural settings. Moreover, they recognized the need to take action by gaining more awareness of cultural diversity, being respectful of other cultures, and preventing past conflict from happening in the future.

Research question two sought to gain insight into South Korean EFL students’ perceptions of intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students discussed their thoughts on discrimination related to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Black Lives Matter movement and racism, prejudice, and discrimination, as well as Korean issues pertaining to intercultural communication. Students identified key issues in the news, and some of these topics had been discussed throughout the semester. However, some students identified topics that had not been heavily discussed in class, especially issues related to North and South Korean relations. In many of the responses regarding students’ perceptions of intercultural issues in the news, students recognized the need for education and action to prevent these types of problems in the future. Global citizenship education aims to foster a sense of social responsibility and action (UNESCO, 2014). If students are going to be agents for change in society, they first have to be cognizant of intercultural issues happening own campus, in their local communities, nationally, and globally. Students were able to identify key intercultural issues in the news and expressed their opinions on these issues. Furthermore, students emphasized the need for intercultural awareness in preventing these types of problems in the future.

The final research question centered on obtaining participant recommendations for improving intercultural communication on a personal level, on campus, and in society. The intercultural communication course focused heavily on principles of global citizenship education, which taught students the importance of taking action in society as responsible citizens. Although the aim of global citizenship, is to create global citizens, students can begin by making changes in their personal lives and within their network. Students should be actively engaged in social issues (O’Dowd, 2019) and strive to improve problems impacting the world (Leask, 2015). Hence, students were asked to recommend ways to improve intercultural communication within their own spheres of influence, especially in their personal lives, on campus, and even in society.

Conclusion

This study sought to gain insight into South Korean EFL students’ perceptions of the importance of intercultural communication as well as their opinions on intercultural issues in the news during the COVID-19 pandemic. Students provided practical recommendations for improving awareness of intercultural communication. By implementing aspects of global citizenship education theory into course assignments and lectures, students could gain a deeper understanding and appreciation of cultural diversity and consider ways to take action and make a difference.

Although this study presented new insight into concepts related to intercultural communication during the COVID-19 pandemic, they need to be carefully interpreted. The participants were limited to one class and cannot be generalized across South Korea or other educational contexts. The class was also conducted online, which was a new experience for the students. Furthermore, students may have shared responses that they felt were ethically sound and may have been hesitant to share honest opinions. Future research should more concretely examine the impact of intercultural communication courses on intercultural competence. Furthermore, intercultural competence should also be studied after course completion to see if students are aware of the concepts taught in class and to examine if students are continuing to learn about intercultural communication and other topics related to cultural diversity. Finally, 2020 has been a year of global crisis, but in the most challenging and trying times often comes reflection and growth. Social issues that have emerged during this pandemic should be further explored and researched in classrooms and on campuses.

References

- Byram, M., Gribkova, B., & Starkey, H. (2002). Developing the intercultural dimension in language teaching: A practical introduction for teachers. *Strasbourg: Council of Europe*. Retrieved from <https://discovery.ucl.ac.uk/id/eprint/1562524/>
- Cho, H. S. (2020). Issues and challenges of educators in implementing global citizenship education in South Korea. *KEDI Journal of Educational Policy*, 14(2), 21-39.
- Cho, H. S., & Mosselson, J. (2018). Neoliberal practices amidst social justice orientations: Global citizenship education in South Korea. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 48(6), 861-878.
- Creswell, J. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design* (2nd ed). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crozet, C., & Liddicoat, A. J. (1999). The challenge of intercultural language teaching: Engaging with culture in the classroom. In Lo Bianco, J. Liddicoat, A. J., Crozet, C. (Eds.), *Striving for the third place: Intercultural competence through language education* (pp. 113-125). Melbourne: Language Australia.
- Hyo, S. A. (2017). Korean EFL students' intercultural learning through a culture integrated program for global citizenship. *Journal of the Korea English Education Society*, 16(3), 1-26. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18649/jkees.2017.16.3.1>
- King, J., Leow, F., Cabarkapa, S., & Ng, C. H. (2020). Addressing international student mental health during COVID-19: An imperative overdue. *Australasian Psychiatry*, 28(4), 469.
- Kramsch, C. (1998). *Language and culture*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Leask, B. (2015). *Internationalising the curriculum*. Abingdon, UK: Routledge.
- Lee, H.-J. (27 November 2020). Foreign residents experience discrimination amid COVID-19. *The Korea Herald*. Retrieved from https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/www/nation/2020/11/177_300037.html
- Li, W., Yang, Y., Ng, C. H., Zhang, L., Zhang, Q., Cheung, T., & Xiang, Y.-T. (2020). Global imperative to combat stigma associated with the coronavirus disease 2019 pandemic. *Psychological Medicine*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291720001993>
- Liu, Y., & Finch, B. K. (2020). Discrimination against Asian, Black Americans more likely amid coronavirus pandemic. Retrieved from <https://healthpolicy.usc.edu/evidence-base/discrimination-against-asian-black-americans-more-likely-amid-coronavirus-pandemic/>
- O'Dowd, R. (2019). A transnational model of virtual exchange for global citizenship education. *Language Teaching*, 53, 477-490. doi: 10.1017/S0261444819000077
- Ock, H.-J. (13 May 2020). Expat community jolted by COVID-19 outbreak in Itaewon. *The Korea Herald*. Retrieved from <http://www.koreaherald.com/view.php?ud=20200512000938>
- Porto, M., & Byram, M. (2015). Developing citizenship education in the language classroom and beyond. *Argentinian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 3(2), 9-29.
- Schwartz, S. J. (2020). Editorial: Studying the effects of the coronavirus pandemic on intercultural relations. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 75(52), 1-2.
- Shimizu, K. (2020). 2019 n-CoV, fake news, and racism. *The Lancet*, 395(10225), 685-686. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(20\)30357-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30357-3)
- Tuncel, I., & Paker, T. (2018). Effects of an intercultural communication course in developing intercultural sensitivity. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 7(6), 198-211.
- Walton, J., Priest, N., & Yin, P. (2013). Identifying and developing effective approaches to foster intercultural understanding in schools. *Intercultural Education*, 24(3), 181-194.
- Zheng, Y., Goh, E., & Wen, J. (2020). The effects of misleading media reports about COVID-19 on Chinese tourists' mental health: A perspective article. *Anatolia*, 31(2), 337-340.
- UNESCO. (2020a). COVID-19 related discrimination and stigma: A global phenomenon? Retrieved from <https://en.unesco.org/news/covid-19-related-discrimination-and-stigma-global-phenomenon>
- UNESCO. (2020b). The socio-cultural impact of COVID-19: Exploring the role of intercultural dialogue in emerging responses. Retrieved from <http://www.unesco-cdsj.com/unesco-chair/new-briefing-paper-the-socio-cultural-impact-of-covid-19-exploring-the-role-of-icd-in-emerging-responses/>
- UNESCO. (2014). Global citizenship education: Preparing learners for the challenges of the 21st century. Retrieved from <https://www.gcedclearinghouse.org/resources/global-citizenship-education-preparing-learners-challenges-21st-century>

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